

IPBES invasive alien species assessment, data management report for Chapter 3. Section 3.2.2.1: Regional and national changes in human population density

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Description

Review of literature for the section 3.2.2.1 Regional and national changes in human population density focusing on the role of human population density as a driver of biological invasions for chapter 3 of IPBES thematic assessment of invasive alien species and their control.

The experts conducted a semi-systematic review to report on the existing knowledge on this driver. This included references provided by experts and a snowball process based on following the citation network of shortlisted papers. This resulted in the data used as evidence for the section.

Process overview

Search 1:

Search 2:

Search 3:

Search 4:

Search 5:

Additional papers added to the selection (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations) n=6

Papers selected for review n=21

Protocol

- **Type of analysis/search/review:** literature review

- **Search language(s):** English

- **Search terms:**

Search 1: "drivers" AND "invasive species"

Search 2: "human population density" AND "invasive species")

Search 3: "human population" AND "invasive species" AND "richness"

Search 4: "invasive species" OR "aliens species" OR "exotic species") AND "human population OR density") 6700 hits

Search 5: "human population density" AND "invasive species" AND "marine"

- **Search engine:** Google scholar

- **Date:** August 2019 to November 2019

- **Overview of the search results and selection criteria:**

Number of search result: 15

Search 1: 2 selected

Search 2: 5 selected

Search 3: 3 selected

Search 4: 4 selected

Search 5: 1 selected

Selection criteria:

Based on the search terms (Search 1 to 5), 15 papers were selected. Additionally, searching the citations of the selected papers resulted in identifying further 2 papers. Then 3 papers added by an expert's knowledge and 1 paper from an external reviewer's recommendation to fill the knowledge gap.

Number of added papers (experts' knowledge and reviewers' recommendations): 6

Added by citation search: 2

Added based on expert's knowledge: 3

Added based on external reviewer's recommendation: 1

- **Step by step analysis (methodology, categories, etc.):**

Number of papers reviewed: 21 (See Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx)

Fields extracted:

- Publication title

- Year of publication

- Invasion stage [Uptake and transport; Introduction; Establishment; Spread]

- Biomes [Terrestrial; Freshwater; Marine]

- Taxon [Plant; Vertebrate; Invertebrate; Microbes]

- Type of study [Primary study; Review; Meta-analysis]

- Region [Europe and Central Asia; Asia-Pacific; Oceania; Americas; Africa]

- Unit of analysis [IPBES units of analysis]

-Cross-cutting theme [Scenarios and models; indigenous and local knowledge; Good quality of life
-Comment (free text)

- **Files:** Chapter 3_literature_review_masterdatabase.xlsx